

Literacy Skills Development for Tertiary Institutions: A Case Study of the University of Calabar

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Abstract

This study is an analysis of information literacy skills (ILS) of undergraduate students. The primary objective of the study was to investigate how students' academic performance can be influenced by the acquisition of literacy skills, that is, the ability to locate and use information. The study also examines the various factors that influence the acquisition of literacy skills. The framework of the analysis is the General Studies (GSS) programme especially the Use of English programme which incorporates library and literacy skills. Data collection instrument used was questionnaire. Two hundred and ninety one (291) respondents participated in this study. These were drawn from five faculties, namely Education, Social Sciences, Law, Arts and Agriculture. The study observed that there is a significant difference among students and faculties in information literacy skills. The factors associated with the observation include the students' background, frequency of attending library and literacy skills lectures, the course contents and mode of instructions, and the general attitudes of the students towards the programme. It is recommended that the course contents should be redesigned and a framework developed for use in the teaching of library and literacy skills. The